

Reactive collision avoidance for the teleoperation of a micro aerial vehicle

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Abstract—Teleoperating an aerial vehicle might not be easy for naive users. A common approach to facilitate this task is to endow the robot with the autonomous capability of avoiding obstacles, while following the user command as much as possible. In this work, we present a reactive collision avoidance algorithm that, based on minimal sensing (monocular RGB camera), allows the safe navigation of a teleoperated micro aerial vehicle (MAV) in complex and unknown environments.

Index Terms—Computer Vision, Aerial Vehicles, Reactive Collision Avoidance, Teleoperation

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) can have different levels of autonomy depending on the human operator’s role in their control: manual flight, semiautonomous, and autonomous [1]. In the semiautonomous case, the UAV is equipped with enough onboard sensors to remain in a stable state even in absence of external inputs, but the user remains responsible of finding feasible paths and avoid obstacles. To ensure a safe navigation also in case of naive pilots, a common approach is to enrich the semiautonomous modality by endowing the robot with the capability of autonomously avoiding obstacles while following the user’s commands [2].

In this abstract, we present a recently submitted work [3] in which we propose a vision-based reactive collision avoidance algorithm exploiting the concept of repulsive force fields. This is intended to facilitate the teleoperation of a micro aerial vehicle (MAV) flying in complex and unknown environments.

Differently from previous work on vision-based collision avoidance for semiautonomous systems [4], [5], we chose to rely on a monocular RGB camera and not on an RGB-D sensor. Thus, in our approach, depth information is not acquired directly, but is reconstructed with an approach based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [6], [7]. In this way, the UAV is endowed with minimal onboard sensing. The adopted strategy for the collision avoidance is based on *virtual force fields*. Similarly to [2], safety zones around the UAV are defined and when an obstacle enters such zones a repulsive force is exerted on the robot to avoid the obstacles. However, while in [2] authors rely on LIDAR measurements and represent objects as cylinders, here we use an RGB camera

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed approach.

and, more importantly, we do not formulate any assumption on the shape of obstacles.

II. METHODOLOGY

The adopted methodology is summarized in the block scheme in Fig. 1. The approach starts by processing an input RGB image collected at the k -th timestep by the camera. The local point cloud in the MAV reference system is computed by first estimating the depth map associated to the image and then back-projecting it in the 3D coordinates. For the depth map estimation, we rely on Monodepth2 [6], whose network mimics the fully convolutional U-Net architecture [7]. After the point cloud generation, voxelization is performed to cluster 3D points and detect obstacles. We indicate with $V = \{v_i | i = 0, 1, \dots, N, v_i \in \Omega\}$ the set containing the N voxels v_i in the camera field of view Ω .

To compute the force feedback signal and perform the collision avoidance, we extend the approach proposed in [2]. In that work, objects are modeled as cylinders with infinite height. While this assumption is reasonable in scenarios with few obstacles and objects with rectangular or cylindrical shapes, it does not apply to more complex and realistic contexts. Furthermore, it requires additional functional blocks responsible for object detection and tracking, which add both computational and system complexity. We propose to detect collision areas and compute force feedback controls by directly processing the voxels computed by the vision module. This increases the system efficiency and flexibility, since less operations need to be performed and it is not limited to predefined obstacle shapes.

Before computing the force feedback command, it is necessary to define the zones that trigger the avoidance procedure.

To this aim, we define three areas with respect to the camera field of view used to perceive the MAV surroundings: the *critical* area Γ , the *avoidance* area Σ and the *detection* area Ψ :

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma &= \{d(v_i) \leq \delta_1 + \alpha, i = 1, 2, \dots, N, v_i \in \Omega\} \\ \Sigma &= \{\delta_1 + \alpha \leq d(v_i) \leq \delta_2 + \alpha, i = 1, 2, \dots, N, v_i \in \Omega\} \\ \Psi &= \{\delta_2 + \alpha \leq d(v_i) \leq \delta_3 + \alpha, i = 1, 2, \dots, N, v_i \in \Omega\},\end{aligned}$$

where α is the radius of the circle enclosing the v_i (which we assume to be the same for all the voxels), and $d(v_i)$ is the distance between each voxel and the MAV.

The Γ area is the most critical, as objects inside it are in proximity of the MAV and collisions are likely to occur. Therefore, the avoidance procedure begins as soon as an object enters in the avoidance zone Σ . Detected obstacles that are outside Σ do not represent an imminent danger and, thus, no force feedback needs to be applied. This zone is represented by the Ψ area.

To compute the force feedback signal, we take advantage and integrate the Adaptive Virtual Cushion Force Field (AVCFF) introduced in [2]. The key idea behind this approach lies in the concept of virtual repulsive force, which acts on the MAV as soon as an obstacle enters in the avoidance area Σ and pushes it away as if it was carrying a safety “cushion”. The role of the force feedback is to recover the original shape of the cushion that has been virtually deformed by the obstacles.

Specifically, for each voxel $v_i \in \{\Sigma, \Gamma\}$ we define the virtual force vector as: $\mathbf{F}_{v_i} = F_{v_i} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{v_i \rightarrow m}$, where F_{v_i} is the magnitude and $\mathbf{n}_{v_i \rightarrow m}$ is the direction pointing from v_i towards the position of the MAV. The magnitude of the repulsive force is computed as follows:

$$F_{v_i} = \begin{cases} F_{max} \cdot \exp^{-\gamma f(d(v_i))} & \text{if } v_i \in \{\Sigma, \Gamma\} \text{ and } F_{v_i} \leq F_{max} \\ F_{max} & \text{if } v_i \in \{\Sigma, \Gamma\} \text{ and } F_{v_i} > F_{max} \\ 0 & \text{if } v_i \notin \{\Sigma, \Gamma\} \end{cases}$$

F_{max} is a user defined hyper-parameter encoding the maximum allowed magnitude for F_{v_i} , γ controls the minimum peripheral distance that gives the maximum repulsive force, and $f(d(v_i))$ computes the peripheral distance between the voxel and the MAV as follows: $f(d(v_i)) = d(v_i) - \alpha - \delta_1$.

The virtual force vectors of each voxel in the avoidance area are then summed and the obtained quantity is integrated over time (and normalized by the MAV mass) to compute the reactive velocity vector \mathbf{v}_r , which replaces the user command (\mathbf{v}_{intent}) to perform the avoidance.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We performed experiments in simulation (Unreal Engine 4 with AirSim plugin) to evaluate the performance of the collision avoidance algorithm when varying different parameters, including δ_2 , F_{max} , and \mathbf{v}_{intent} , and in complex realistic scenarios like the one displayed in Fig. 2. In the first set of experiments we found that, even if for large values of δ_2 and F_{max} the navigation is safe as the MAV tends to avoid obstacles soon and with a high repulsive force, the robot

Fig. 2. MAV avoiding an obstacle in a complex outdoor environment.

motion deviates a lot from the user command. Thus, a trade-off between safety and adherence to the desired velocity should be found. Then we observed that even for rather high commanded velocities (up to $\mathbf{v}_{intent} = [0, 5, 0]$ m/s) no collisions occur in a structured scenario. To conclude, we tested the proposed algorithm in three different Park environments with several obstacles commanding a desired velocity $\mathbf{v}_{intent} = [0, 2, 0]$ m/s. Two conditions were evaluated: in the first, the height of the drone was kept fixed, whereas in the second it was free to vary. Out of the conducted 30 trials, no collision was found and the MAV followed well, on average, the desired velocity.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a reactive collision avoidance system for a micro aerial vehicle and is the first step towards a framework for supporting pilots during the remote control of MAVs. In future work we plan to use wearable feedback interfaces for increasing human awareness during the task and to allow the drone not only to follow a commanded velocity but also to track a complete trajectory.

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